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S.No	CONTENT	Page No
1	Enhancing Talent Management - Dr. P. Aasish Nahar	1
2	Role of Team Leadership in Enhancing Effective Team Performance: A Review - Dr. Buvaneswari & P. S - Kuralmozhi .C	5
3	Impact of Training and Development on the Effectiveness of Employees in Public Sector Banks- R.H. Abdul Hajee	11
4	Talent Management - A.M. Abid Basha	16
5	Leveraging Online Marketing - M.H. Amreen Akthar	20
6	Incorporating Sustainable Marketing Beyond Conventional Ceilings – Amrutha R	25
7	Role of Human Resource Management Practice in Employee Performance (A Special Reference to HOV Service in Chennai) - V. Gunasekaran	29
8	Exploring The Employability Gap Among The Graduates: A Holistic Approach - B. Fuzail Ahmed	33
9	Impact of Employee Retention Strategies on India’s Private Sector - Karpagavalli	36
10	Building & Retaining High Performance Teams - M. Kiruthika	40
11	Sustaining High Performance Employees and Enhancing Talent Management - M. Kotteeswari	44
12	Soft Skills Training: A Quality for High Performance Team - K. Madhu	48
13	Evolution of E-Commerce into M-Commerce in India - A.M.Z. Mohammed Arsath Ali	52
14	Emerging Opportunities in Rural Markets- J. Murali Krishnan	55
15	Standardizing Excellence Through Organizational / Business Communication - Nabeel Ahmed	61
16	E-commerce & Supply Chain Management Fitting the Pieces Together- N. Purusothaman	65
17	E-Commerce and its Emerging Trends- E. Sathiya Moorthi	68
18	Impact of Taxes on Economic Growth- P.G. Sidheakky	72
19	Recruitment, Reward and Retention- R. Shiva Shankar	75
20	Trade and Globalization –T. Samira Sultana	78
21	Recent Trends in E-Commerce – B. Syed Asif. & K. Annapoorani	82

22	Antecedents and Consequences of Employee Engagement in Banks- V. Tharanya	86
23	An Empirical Study to Understand the Changing Employee Needs and Expectations and its Impact on Retaining Quality Faculty with Reference to Educational Institutions in Chennai -Dr. Lalitha Balakrishnan & M. Vijayalakshmi	91
24	Entrepreneurial Motivation and its Impact on Business Performance of Women Entrepreneurs with Reference to Chennai - Dr. S.Veeramani	96
25	A Study on the Impact of Advertisements of Health Food Drinks with Reference to Chennai - E. Ravichandran	106
26	Emerging Opportunities in Indian Rural Market- M. Kamaladevi	115
27	Emerging Oppurtunities in Rural Marketing in India – K. Janaki & A.C. Deepthi	119
28	E- Commerce and its Emerging Trends in India Dr. K. Natarajan	125
29	Jaina logic is Best for Artificial Intelligence R.Malathi T.Venugopal	132
30	Implementation of Information and Communication Technology with Three Dimenstional Graphical Representation by using the Open Source Mathematics Software Geogebra J.Sengamalaselvi T.Venugopal	141

28. E-Commerce and its Emerging Trends in India

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Abstract

Asia-Pacific emerged as the strongest business-to consumer (B2C) e-commerce region in the world in 2013 with sales of around 567.3 billion USD, a growth of 45 percent over 2012, ranking ahead of Europe (482.3 billion USD) and North America (452.4 billion USD). The top three were followed by Latin America, and the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region, according to E-commerce Europe1. Globally, B2C e-commerce sales increased by 24 percent over 2012. This reflects the huge untapped potential of e-commerce by retail companies, both in their country of origin and across borders. E-commerce or electronic commerce, deals with the buying and selling of goods and services, or the transmitting of funds or data, over an electronic platform, mainly the internet. These business transactions are categorised into either business-to-business (B2B), business-to-consumer (B2C), consumer-to-consumer (C2C), consumer-to-business (C2B) or the recently evolved business-to-business-to-consumer (B2B2C). E-commerce processes are conducted using applications, such as email, fax, online catalogues and shopping carts, electronic data interchange (EDI), file transfer protocol and web services and e-newsletters to subscribers. E-Travel is the most popular form of e-commerce, followed by e-Tail which essentially means selling of retail goods on the internet conducted by the B2C category. This paper describes the current trends of e-commerce and its future.

Key words – E-commerce, e-tail, Business-to Business, retail, Consumer

Introduction

E-commerce in recent times has been growing rapidly across the world. According to Report of Digital-Commerce, IAMAI-IMRB (2013), e-commerce industry in India has witnessed a growth of US\$ 3.8 billion in the year 2009 to US\$ 9.5 billion in 2012. By 2013, the market is expected to reach US\$12.6 billion, showing year to year growth of 34%. Industry sources indicate that this growth can be sustained over a longer period of time as e-commerce will continue to reach new geographies and encompass new markets. E-commerce means sale or purchase of goods and services conducted over network of computers or TV channels by methods specifically designed for the purpose. Even though goods and services are ordered electronically, payments or delivery of goods and services need not be conducted online. E-commerce transaction can be between businesses, households, individuals, governments and other public or private organizations.

Over the last decade, the Internet has changed the way people buy and sell goods and services. Online retail or e-commerce is transforming the shopping experience of customers. The sector has seen unprecedented growth especially in the last two years. The adoption of technology is enabling the e-commerce sector to be more reachable and efficient. Devices like smartphones, tablets and technologies like 3G, 4G, Wi-Fi and high speed broadband is helping to increase the number of online customers. Banks and other players in e-commerce ecosystem are providing a secured online platform to pay effortlessly via payments gateways. The homegrown

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players have shown tremendous growth and attracted some big investors. The entry of global biggies like Amazon and Alibaba has taken the competition to a new level. E-tailers are differentiating themselves by providing innovative service offerings like one-day delivery, 30-day replacement warranty, cash on delivery (CoD), cashback offers, mobile wallets, etc. The supply chain has improved significantly and e-tailers are even leveraging on the services of Indian Post for greater reach across the country. In 2014, Indian Post collected 2.8 billion through CoD option of payment. India slipped from 14th to 20th rank among the top 30 developing countries in 2014 Global Retail Development Index (GRDI) that looks at measures for retail investments worldwide. Chile and China are leading in the GRDI rankings. The sector is still in its growth stage in India and has enormous potential to offer in the coming years. The government's most prestigious Digital India project could take the sector to new heights.

There are numerous types of e-commerce transactions that occur online ranging from sale of clothes, shoes, books etc. to services such as airline tickets or making hotel bookings etc.

- The bookings done through electronic communication could be Business to Business (B2B) or Business to Consumer (B2C). Business to Business i.e. B2B is e-commerce between businesses such as between a manufacturer and a wholesaler or between a wholesaler and a retailer. As per the WTO report WT/COMTD/W/193, global B2B transactions comprise 90 percent of all e-commerce.
- The bookings done electronically between Business to Consumer for purchase or sale of goods and services is known as B2C e-commerce. Although B2C e-commerce receives a lot of attention, B2B transactions far exceed B2C transactions. B2C e-Commerce entails business selling to general public/ e-catalogues that make use of shopping place. There are several variants in B2C model that operate in e-commerce arena.
- From the point of view of business, there are two models of e-commerce. First model is known as Market Place model, which works like exchange for buyers and sellers. The Market Place provides a platform for business transactions between buyers and sellers to take place and in return for the services provided, earns commission from sellers of goods/services. Ownership of the inventory in this model vests with the number of enterprises which advertise their products on the website and are ultimate sellers of goods or services.

Role of Retailers online

The big retailers are trying to complement the traditional retailing with digital commerce by tying up with big e-tailers. The partnership between Snapdeal & Croma or Amazon & Future Group owned Big Bazaar is no more a partnership between two retailers. It has extended to a vendor and technology partners offering technology and logistics services. Reliance retail is planning to launch its e-commerce website seeking to attract people from online retailers. Shoppers Stop is revamping its digital platform, which currently contributes 1 percent of the revenue. The extended reach of the online channel is the primary reason for offline retailers to launch e-commerce offerings. India's e-commerce market is set to hit \$76 billion by 2021 from \$13.6 billion in 2014, according to e-Tailing India. However, as business model changes have

become more frequent and delivery more complex, increasing innovation in promotion, pricing, sale, and even distribution channels will be seen going forward. Entrepreneurial ecosystem is evolving with innovative startups capturing the mass market of India and taking opportunity in solving some of the big challenges faced by the country.

Impact of Modern Technologies

The pace of technology change is very fast and individuals, businesses and Governments need to be in sync with it. Internet and smartphones are becoming an integral part of every life. Internet is no more a source of information, but has become an important tool for shopping, learning, working, communicating and even connecting with plumbers, carpenters, doctors, etc. SMBs and large enterprises are also embracing advanced technologies to stay in business. Several industries including retail are going digital and online to increase the reach and to better connect with customers. Supply chains are becoming leaner and smarter as digital platforms are helping to connect buyers and sellers directly. The rise of Internet, smartphone and social media users have made analytics an integral part of any digital business. There is abundance of customer data in every business including e-commerce and analytics helps in deriving meaningful insights to help the business in growing and serving the customers better. The availability of e-commerce applications on various mobility devices is helping to drive sales and revenue.

Growth of Payment Gateways

When it comes to running an online business the crucial part is how the customer will pay. An e-commerce payment gateway is a service that authorizes credit card, debit card or online banking payments and processes them securely with a user's merchant account for electronic fund transfer (EFT). The world is moving from cash to digital money and thus there is a need of payment gateway for sustainable future e-commerce. The Indian e-commerce sector is heavily dependent on Cash on Delivery (CoD) mode of payment as it is the most preferred choice for Indian consumers due to lack of trust in online transactions, limited adoption of credit/debit cards, and security concerns among others. More than 50% of online transactions are done on cash on delivery method and it is available across 600 cities and towns of India.

Payment gateways help the e-tailers to receive money instantly rather than waiting for the CoD payments, thus reducing chances of theft and fraud. The retailers are slowly moving towards payment gateways for improving security and dealing with other complexities which arise with financial transactions. The banks as well as the e-tailers are offering different offers like cashback and easy Easy Monthly Installment (EMI) to encourage customers for card-based payments. Startups like Paytm and FreeCharge are providing mobile wallets while almost every commercial bank is providing the option to pay online via credit or debit card. The popular EMI option which can be availed by credit card users with online payment are luring customer to pay online upfront for high-value items. The payment gateways use various security measures such One Time Password (OTP), CVV in case of debit/credit card, etc.

Impact of Social Media

Social networks have started to play a significant role in the growth of the e-commerce business. The maturity of social media and its reach across masses and classes makes it a suitable platform for online sales. Social media pages provide information regarding new products in the market, user reviews and ratings of the product, recommendations, share products, etc. Social media also helps e-tailers to build brand awareness by responding to customer queries. Seasonal sales and offers are displayed in social networks to reach maximum number of people. E-tailers have even started to motivate customers with reward points to provide feedback on the product on social networks. Prospective customers also interact with users of the product or service on social networks before making purchase decision. Increasingly social networks have direct links to e-commerce sites, which provide complete product description, availability status, pricing and delivery information, and access to product reviews and ratings, all of which help prospective buyers to make a purchase.

The social media provides a platform for e-tailers to engage with customers for:

- Advertisement
- Building brand awareness
- Developing a community of trusted users
- Spreading Word-of-Mouth
- Customer feedback

Status of the global e-commerce industry:

The biggest e-commerce markets are U.S.A. followed by U.K. and Japan. In Asia, China, India and Indonesia are the fastest growing e-commerce markets. Major global e-commerce companies are Alibaba.com, Amazon.com, Walmart, Apple, Dell, e-bay, Mercadolibre Inc., Rakuten Inc., Crate & Barrel, Symantec, Autozone, Microsoft, Gap, Nike, Disney stores, HP, ASOS PLC, Blue Nile Inc. etc.

Role of India Post in e-Commerce Route

India Post has a potential to emerge as world's leading e-commerce delivery platform, India Post had updated itself with latest technological developments in the country and has tied up with more than 400 e-commerce agencies including Flipkart, Amazon and Snapdeal for delivering e-commerce pre-paid as well as Cash-on-Delivery orders. Amazon is the largest business partner of India Post's e-Commerce division. The parcel revenue, which registered a 2 per cent decline in 2013-14, had clocked 37 per cent growth in 2014-15 and further grew by 117 per cent during the first half of 2015-16. India Post posted total revenue of ₹. 11,636 crores during 2014-15, with post and parcel related services accounting for 42 per cent of the revenue. Spread over 12,000 sq feet, the e-commerce Parcel Processing Centre at Parel is fully mechanized and computerised using conveyer belts, scanners, computers and electronic weighing scales. It has also been provided with a dedicated transport facility to dispatch parcel bags to Mumbai Airport. Currently, the centre processes around 7,000 e-commerce parcels per day and has an installed capacity to handle 30,000 e-commerce parcels in a day in three shifts. The quick delivery of e-commerce parcels is done through four dedicated mechanised nodal

delivery centres which cover 21 delivery post offices in Mumbai. Soon remaining post offices in Mumbai would also be equipped with mechanised nodal delivery system which will ensure that parcels could be delivered on Sundays as well as holidays and customers can track their parcels in real time on Indian Post website.

Plans of India's Leading E-Commerce Firms

Indian e-commerce companies such as Snapdeal, Flipkart, and Paytm featured on the leader board of the highest funded Internet companies in India in 2015. Backed with funding from Softbank and Alibaba Group, these three also figured on the list of most acquisitive startup in India in 2015. In 2016, the e-commerce landscape promises to get bigger and wider, as Reliance and the Tata group plan to launch its own e-commerce platform to take on global players like Amazon, which had pledged a \$2 billion (roughly ` 13314 crores) war chest to establish a lasting foothold in the Indian e-commerce market. Indian e-commerce market opportunity was measured in "trillions of dollars". For Snapdeal, 2015 was a significant year where it refreshed the consumer experience, launched Shopo, Free Charge wallet, and made moves in the (Online to Offline) space, and refreshed the seller experience, launching an ads platform.

Bridging offline and online

Snapdeal, highlighted the company's improvements in its core e-commerce processes such as logistics and delivery capabilities, and quicker returns and refunds. "2016 is the year that e-commerce matures and becomes a habit for consumers," "They will start to think less of it as something they do once in a while, and more like something they completely trust and rely on for everyday needs." Snapdeal will continue to focus on providing a reliable delivery experience, which it views as a major USP. "During the Diwali season, Snapdeal met the delivery promises 98 percent of the time when orders were 9x more than the average day,". "This will be a key differentiator in the industry."

Flipkart, Paytm, and Snapdeal all have offline tie-ups with mobile retailers, electronics retailers and automobile dealerships to power online to offline purchases. Snapdeal intends to leverage its deep integration with Free Charge to enhance its offline presence. A user's identity, stored cash, and address details can be carried with the customer, and power its omni-channel platform that combines e-commerce with the flexibility of buying goods offline. The offline to online strategy is one that Paytm has also seen success with. Once an order is placed, it's routed to the nearest shore of that chain, it works well for large appliances and electronics. Paytm has tied up with local and large format retailers across the country, to get their products listed on its marketplace, and is intensifying its efforts to expand its reach and bring in big brands across different products and services. Paytm has also significantly improved its logistics services, adding third-party or partner warehouses to enable merchants to deliver products faster to the consumers. Shorter delivery times for the consumer results in an improved conversion rate. Paytm also recently acquired the virtual assistant app Shifu to enhance its consumer behaviour prediction capabilities. The company is interested in investments and acquisitions in areas like artificial intelligence, logistics and offline to online.

For Snapdeal, this strategy was essential for the launch of its motors and real estate sections. "It used this platform onboard 4,000 to 5,000 (vehicle) dealers into the system," As a result of that, their inventory, what colour they had, of the two wheelers or the four wheelers. That was a big part of those successful launches for them. They sold over 3 lakh vehicles built on top of the O2O platform."

An evolving marketplace

Mobile-only fashion retailer Myntra has a goal of hitting \$1 billion GMV (roughly ` 6661 crores) in 2016, and to be completely profitable the year after that. "The third goal is to improve customer experience significantly," On that front, it includes more investments in logistics, a more personalised shopping experience, better brands and selection on the app, and to make sure that the experience is very social, so that one can actually get the kind of thing that would like to buy, and get the feedback from your friends and family,". Myntra has piloted Try and Buy and alteration services in Bengaluru, and is looking to scale these features across the country once it finds the infrastructure to support it. On the product side, the app has seen a change in the UX with features like Fashion feed, Profile, and Forum. Myntra doing a lot more on entertainment as well - so launched a game called Fashionable Fingers, where people can play a quiz game about fashion and win prizes,". "Things of this sort make it social, because one can share the questions with your friend, get their help in answering, move up the leader board, and engage people around fashion in India. All of these are attempts to do those two things that will continue to be focus - personalisation, and social."

Conclusion

The e-commerce market in India has grown by 34 percent in the last seven years, was about USD 600 million in 2011-12 and is expected to touch USD 9 billion by 2016 and USD 70 billion by 2020. According to Forrester, the Indian e-commerce market is expected to grow at a CAGR of over 57 percent between 2012 and 2016, which is the fastest within Asia-Pacific region. The key factors that are driving this growth are the rise of Internet usage (growing at 20 percent) & 3G penetration, and increasing smartphone users with availability of Internet on mobile phones. It is estimated that currently there are 27 million mobile Internet users in India out of which 4 percent are buying products on mobile. Overall, e-commerce including online retail in India constitutes a small fraction of total sales, but is set to grow to a substantial amount owing to a lot of factors such as rising disposable incomes, rapid urbanization, increasing adoption and penetration of technology such as the internet and mobiles, rising youth population as well as increasing cost of running offline stores across the country. A key outcome of the technology revolution in India has been connectivity, which has fuelled unprecedented access to information. Rural Indians recognise the differences between the opportunities available to them and those available to their urban counterparts. And citizens have a mass forum for expressing their political opinions. The upshot of this connectivity revolution has been empowerment of Indians.

Reference

1. Social Commerce Retail 2013: <http://www.minimarketing.it/wp-content/uploads/2014/02/Social-Commerce-IQ-Retail-2013.pdf>.
2. Future of e-Commerce: Uncovering Innovation www.deloitte.com/in
3. <http://www.pwc.in/assets/pdfs/publications/2015/ecommerce-in-india-accelerating-growth.pdf>
4. Indian Post collected Rs 280 crore through COD. See: <http://www.bgr.in/news/india-post-collects-rs-280-crore-through-cash-on-delivery-for-ecommerce-firms-like-flipkart-snapdeal-and-amazon/>
5. GRDI rankings: India's profile as destination for retail investment diminishes. See: <http://www.livemint.com/Industry/1IMrxCz9849nUVCE2QyHbN/RDI-rankings-Indias-profile-as-destination-for-retail-inv.html>
6. E-Commerce Industry In India Worth \$13.5 Billion In 2014, March 2015. <http://dazeinfo.com/2015/03/19/e-commerce-industry-india-worth-13-5-billion-2014-will-cross-16-billion-2015/>
7. Most people in big cities are shopping online: Visa, March 2015. http://economictimes.indiatimes.com/articleshow/46709327.cms?utm_source=contentofinterest&utm_medium=text&utm_campaign=cppst
8. Global B2C Ecommerce Sales to Hit \$1.5 Trillion This Year Driven by Growth in Emerging Markets, Feb 2014. See: <http://www.emarketer.com/>
9. Article/Global-B2C-Ecommerce-Sales-Hit-15-Trillion-This-Year-Driven-by-Growth-Emerging-Markets/1010575
10. Shoppers Stop eyeing bigger play in online space, Feb 2015. See: http://www.business-standard.com/article/pti-stories/shoppers-stop-eyeing-bigger-play-in-online-space-115020100113_1.html
11. Brick-and-mortar chains gird for battle with e-tailers, March 2015. See: <http://www.hindustantimes.com/business-news/brick-and-mortar-chains-gird-for-battle-with-etailers/article1-1326730.aspx>
12. Cash-on-delivery: Necessary Evil, Feb 2014. See: <http://businesstoday.intoday.in/story/cash-on-delivery-impact-on-e-commerce-companies-customers/1/202680.html>
13. How Much Online Business Is Done Every 30 Seconds? Incredible E-Commerce Statistics!, July 2014. See: <http://www.adweek.com/socialtimes/real-time-ecommerce/499958>
14. The importance of social media in e-commerce, Feb 2014. <http://www.thedrum.com/news/2014/02/16/infographic-importance-social-media-e-commerce>.
15. <http://www.thehindu.com/news/cities/mumbai/news/india-post-can-emerge-as-global-ecommerce-delivery-hub-prasad/article8087948.ece>
16. A Look at 2016 Plans of India's Leading E-Commerce Firms - <http://gadgets.ndtv.com/apps/features/a-look-at-2016-plans-of-indias-leading-e-commerce-firms-786309>